

lasigeBioTM at MedHop track : Can a Lean RAG-Enhanced Model Compete with MedGemma?

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Abstract

Multi-step question answering (QA) is a challenging task that requires integrating evidence from multiple documents to correctly answer complex queries. In the BioCreative IX Track 1: MedHopQA challenge, our team, lasigeBioTM, explored whether lightweight language models can be competitive with larger, domain-specialized models by leveraging retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). We implemented a RAG-based system using Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3, enriched with external knowledge from Wikipedia and the Mondo ontology, and compared its performance to the MedGemma-27B, a larger specialized biomedical model. Despite the added external knowledge, our results show that the lightweight system fell short of matching the performance of MedGemma. However, in the unofficial runs, MedGemma benefited from additional information provided by the ontology, showing that the injection of specialized domain knowledge enhances the performance of the baseline model. These results also highlight the limitations of smaller models in complex domain-specific QA tasks. The code is publicly available at https://github.com/lasigeBioTM/BioCreativeIX_Track1_MedHopQA.

Keywords

Chain-of-Thought, LLM, Lean LLMs, Ontology, RAG

1. Introduction

Most Question Answering (QA) methods rely on queries that can be answered using a single document. However, in real-world scenarios, answering questions often requires combining information from multiple documents. For example, when investigating drug-drug interactions, relevant insights may be dispersed across various publications, highlighting the need for multi-step reasoning [1], therefore, multi-step reasoning is essential. In multi-step reasoning, a model should be capable of answering queries by integrating evidence from various documents [1].

The advent of Large Language Models (LLMs) has significantly enhanced many natural language processing tasks. Although, in QA, these models frequently struggle with the multi-source and grounded knowledge essential for medical reasoning, particularly in complex scenarios [2]. This limitation highlights the importance of developing models that can navigate these scenarios.

In this work, we present our team's participation in the BioCreative IX Track 1: MedHopQA [3]. This track offers a curated dataset of 1,000 question-answer pairs that focus on diseases, genes, and chemicals from publicly available Wikipedia data, with emphasis on rare diseases. This dataset serves as a benchmark for LLM-based systems in answering multi-step reasoning questions related to diseases.

Despite their capabilities, LLMs are often associated with substantial computational resource requirements, rendering them less suitable for resource-constrained environments. Therefore, it is important to explore alternatives that prioritize reliability while minimizing power consumption and computational resources. This advancement is necessary for various aspects, including cost efficiency, scalability and accessibility. Models with these characteristics would allow smaller research groups to remain

Challenge and Workshop (BC9): Large Language Models for Clinical and Biomedical NLP, International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI), August 16–22, 2025, Montreal, Canada

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competitive without the need for high-performance computing. Also, these models could be deployed on local servers in healthcare settings, ensuring better data privacy.

Our goal in this study was to evaluate whether the implementation of Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) and Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting with the lean Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3 model could achieve satisfactory performance levels. We also aimed to assess how this performance compares to that of the larger state-of-the-art MedGemma 27B model.

2. Related Work

Multi-step QA is more challenging than single hop questions, and research has been increasing in recent years.

One approach is Chain-of-Questions framework proposed by Zhu et al. [4]. This framework trains a model to generate sub-questions and sub-answers sequentially. The model generates sub-questions and their corresponding sub-answers one at a time, subsequently aggregating these sub-answers to provide a final answer to the original question. The results demonstrate that this approach outperforms single-step methods.

Building on the need for more effective retrieval methods, Zhang et al. [5] proposed Beam Retrieval, an end-to-end framework for multi-hop question answering. Unlike traditional retrievers that are often customized for two-hop questions and trained separately across different hops, Beam Retrieval jointly optimizes the retrieval process across all hops. It maintains multiple partial hypotheses (beams) of relevant passages at each step, expanding the search space and reducing the risk of missing important information.

Su et al. [2] developed, KGAREvion, a LLM agent designed for complex biomedical QA that integrates structured knowledge from a knowledge graph (KG). This model combines the non-codified knowledge embedded in LLMs with the structured, codified knowledge found in KG. Using zero-shot generalization, this model can dynamically adapt its reasoning strategies to answer complex medical queries in both multi-choice and open-ended QA formats.

Similarly, Chen et al. [6] introduced GMeLLO (Graph Memory-based Editing for Large Language Models), a framework that integrates knowledge graphs with LLMs to address the challenges of multi-hop QA, particularly in dynamic environments. GMeLLO employs LLMs to convert unstructured language into structured queries and fact triples, facilitating seamless interaction with KGs for rapid updates and precise multi-hop reasoning. This approach enables the system to handle knowledge updates efficiently, ensuring that the LLM remains current with the latest information.

3. Methodology

3.1. MedHop Track

3.1.1. Dataset

The original test set that included 1,000 question-answer pairs, was concealed within a collection of 10,000 questions. Each question is curated by referencing two related Wikipedia pages. These pairs are intended to evaluate a system's capability to extract, connect, and interpret disease-related information, including signs and symptoms, genetic details, and treatments.

3.1.2. Evaluation

The primary evaluation metric is Exact Match (EM), where a prediction is considered correct if it exactly matches the gold answer after normalization and synonym handling. Additionally, concept-level correctness will be recognized, which compares the responses at the concept level using curated synonym dictionaries and biomedical ontologies. Lastly, for long-answer evaluation it will be considered reasoning-level evaluation which compares the explanation and the reasoning for a given answer. For

the task, final assessment and shared task recognition will take into account EM and concept-level correctness.

3.2. LLM Models

In this work, we utilized the following models: MedGemma 27B integrated via the Unsloth library¹, Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3² and Gemma-3-1B-IT from Google³.

MedGemma [7] is a specialized variant of Gemma 3, trained exclusively on medical texts. This model is dedicated solely to text processing and features 27 billion parameters, specifically designed to enhance the understanding of complex medical texts and improve clinical reasoning. Its integration into Unsloth allows for up to 60% lower memory consumption and a 1.6-fold increase in processing speed. Unsloth [8] is an open-source library designed to facilitate faster fine-tuning of LLMs while reducing memory usage and maintaining accuracy. We specifically employed the `unsloth/medgemma-27b-text-it-unsloth-bnb-4bit` model, a 4-bit quantized version of MedGemma.

Gemma 3 1B [9] is a lightweight open-source multimodal model from Google with a large 128k token context window. Its compact size makes it suitable for deployment in resource-constrained environments, as it can run on a single GPU.

Mistral-7B-Instruct is an instructive version of Mistral-7B-v0.3 [10], which is a generative text model fine-tuned using a variety of publicly available conversation datasets. It is designed to follow instructions and complete requests effectively. We selected Mistral as the main model for our systems due to constraints related to GPU availability, as access to the NVIDIA A30 was not consistently guaranteed. Our prior experience with Mistral in other projects, where we utilized only the Tesla T4 GPU, demonstrated its stable performance and minimal occurrence of hallucinations, making it a suitable fit for our systems.

3.2.1. Hardware and parameters

The inference was performed on an NVIDIA A30 for MedGemma. Due to varying GPU availability during the challenge, the inference was performed either on an NVIDIA A30 or on a Tesla T4 GPU for Mistral and Gemma. Mistral and Gemma were loaded in 4-bit precision using the BitsAndBytes library⁴, with nested double quantization and Normal Float 4 as quantization type. For the Mistral and Gemma models, the temperature was set to 0.2, and the maximum number of new tokens was limited to 1024, while the remaining parameters were maintained at their default values. For the MedGemma model, only the default parameters were used.

3.3. External Sources

We used the Mondo Disease Ontology (Mondo) and Wikipedia [11] data to perform retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). **Mondo** [12], is an ontology that unifies disease resources in a logic-based structure. It includes cross-reference sources for disease definitions and data from widely used ontologies such as The Human Phenotype Ontology [13], OMIM [14], SNOMED CT [15], Disease Ontology [16] and many others. This project offers a hierarchical structure for classifying diseases and grouping them into higher-level categories. It includes mappings to other disease resources, providing precise annotations for each mapping using strict semantics. We used the main OWL edition, which includes the complete ontology plus inter-ontology equivalence axioms⁵.

¹<https://huggingface.co/unsloth/medgemma-27b-text-it-unsloth-bnb-4bit>

²<https://huggingface.co/mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3>

³<https://huggingface.co/google/gemma-3-1b-it>

⁴<https://huggingface.co/docs/bitsandbytes/main/en/index>.

⁵Data accessed on May 30, 2025, from <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/mondo.owl>

Additionally, we performed RAG based on **Wikipedia** content. Using the Python Wikipedia API⁶, we linked relevant entities to their corresponding Wikipedia pages and extracted the introductory section of each article for a knowledge grounder answer.

3.4. Workflow

The main steps of the used methodology are summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of the MedHopQA workflow. Baseline models received the original query, meanwhile models employing RAG approach received additional information from either Wikipedia or Mondo ontology.

We used two baseline systems, **MedGemma baseline** and **Gemma baseline**, which are systems where only the original question was provided to the LLM and nothing more.

For models using RAG, we implemented the following pipeline: First, we performed named-entity recognition using Mistral in order to extract relevant biomedical entities from the question. The prompt used is provided at Appendix A. Next, we mapped the extracted entities to Mondo Ontology labels in order to retrieve their Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) and corresponding definitions. From the initial 12,949 entities, only 11,963 were linked to a Mondo URI, and from those only 1,641 had available definitions. An example of an entity and the respective information extracted from Mondo:

- **Entity:** sickle cell disease
- **URI:** http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MONDO_0011382
- **Definition:** Sickle cell anemias are chronic hemolytic diseases that may induce three types of acute accidents: severe anemia, severe bacterial infections, and ischemic vasoocclusive accidents (VOA) caused by sickle-shaped red blood cells obstructing small blood vessels and capillaries. Many diverse complications can occur

After this step, there are two different RAG approaches, one that uses ontology definitions and another that uses Wikipedia data.

For ontology definitions RAG, we used **Mistral Onto** system, was provided with the question and the entities' definition and designed a Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompt (refer to Appendix A).

As for RAG using Wikipedia data, we used **Mistral Wiki**. For this system, we provided the mistral model with the introductory information contained within Wikipedia pages for all matched entities at each query, in the format shown in Appendix A. Due to network errors and ambiguities derived from entities referring to multiple Wikipedia pages, we were able to extract 7461 pages and their respective initial content.

⁶<https://pypi.org/project/wikipedia/>

3.5. Unofficial Runs

The organization gracefully permitted us to submit additional runs after reviewing the official submissions and offering suggestions for improvement.

For these runs, we selected our previously best performing model, MedGemma, and performed RAG using the ontology definitions and Wikipedia information, similarly to the approach used for the Mistral model in the official runs.

4. Results and Discussion

We report the concept level (CL) and exact match (EM) scores for our submissions evaluated at the CodaLab Leaderboard. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

CodaLab Submission Results

Runs	Submission ID	System	Concept Level	Exact Match
1	302516	MedGemma Baseline	0.342	0.283
2	302514	Gemma Baseline	0.181	0.125
3	302515	MistralWiki	0.218	0.187
4	302503	Mistral Onto	0.218	0.187
Average			0.591	0.526
Median			0.659	0.594

The best performing system was MedGemma baseline achieving the highest CL and EM scores of 0.342 and 0.283 respectively. This was followed by the two RAG systems, MistralWiki and MistralOnto, both with a CL of 0.218 and EM of 0.187. Finally, we have Gemma baseline with CL of 0.181 and EM of 0.125. These results suggest that system performance correlates with both model scale and domain specialization.

While RAG-based systems achieved better results than Gemma baseline, they still were very behind the much larger and domain-specialized MedGemma. This highlights that the provided external information was not sufficient to allow small, less specialized models perform well on domain-specific tasks.

Both Gemma and MedGemma share the same underlying architecture, but they differ in size and training data. MedGemma is a 27B parameter model trained on medical corpora, while Gemma is a smaller, general purpose 1B model. This discrepancy in scale and specialization explains such a performance gap, as MedGemma has a higher capacity, leading to more accurate predictions in biomedical QA tasks.

4.1. Unofficial Evaluation Phase

The exact match scores for our unofficial submissions evaluated at the CodaLab Leaderboard are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2

CodaLab Unofficial Submission Results

Runs	Submission ID	System	Concept Level	Exact Match
1	313086	MedGemma Onto	0.614	0.562
2	313274	MedGemma Wiki	0.402	0.365

The system that performed better in this phase was MedGemma Onto with a Concept Level score of 0.614 and an Exact Match score of 0.562. This score was achieved by combining the domain trained MedGemma and the specialized ontology information. The disparity between both systems is a result

of different information sources, whereas MedGemma Wiki combines the same model with Wikipedia page information that is unstructured and noisy compared to the ontology information.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

In our work, we compared the performance of the lean model Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3 and the recent MedGemma 27B. Our results show that even though Mistral benefits from the injection of external knowledge, it is not enough to match the performance of MedGemma baseline. In the unofficial runs, the best performing system was MedGemma Onto, which achieved an Exact Match score of 0.562 and a Concept Level of 0.614. This result demonstrates the impact of integrating domain-trained language models with structured, high-quality ontology information. In comparison, MedGemma Wiki, which uses the same underlying model but is paired with Wikipedia content, achieved a slightly better Exact Match score of 0.365 compared to its baseline of 0.283. This large difference in scores between MedGemma Onto and MedGemma Wiki underscores the importance of high-quality and domain specific external-sources of information in boosting system accuracy.

Moreover, RAG-based models' performance is restricted by the quality and coverage of the knowledge provided. In our case, we have only mapped 1,641 entities along with their definitions. This means that for most entities, there is a lack of additional information that could have enhanced the model's performance. Similarly, only a portion of our entities was mapped to their definitions or Wikipedia pages. This indicates that for a significant portion of entities, the models lacked sufficient external knowledge to enhance their performance. The results highlight the limitations of smaller models in complex domain-specific QA tasks.

5.1. Future Work

In future work, we aim to improve entity mapping by incorporating advanced named-entity linking techniques to better disambiguate entities and provide broader, more accurate mappings to the target ontology.

Another promising direction is fine-tuning smaller language models and integrating them with our current RAG approaches to enhance performance.

Additionally, further development could focus on generating a structured knowledge graph from the biomedical free text found in Wikipedia and leveraging its inter-page references to enrich the graph.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by FCT (Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia) through funding of the PhD Scholarships with ref. UI/BD/153730/2022 and DOI identifier <https://doi.org/10.54499/UI/BD/153730/2022> attributed to SIRC, and the LASIGE Research Unit, ref. UID/00408/2025.

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors used GPT-4 and LanguageTool in order to: Grammar, spelling check and paraphrase. Further, the authors used GPT-4 for figure 1 in order to: Generate icons. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication's content.

References

- [1] J. Welbl, P. Stenetorp, S. Riedel, Constructing datasets for multi-hop reading comprehension across documents, *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics* 6 (2018) 287–302. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/Q18-1021/>. doi:10.1162/tacl_a_00021.
- [2] X. Su, Y. Wang, S. Gao, X. Liu, V. Giunchiglia, D.-A. Clevert, M. Zitnik, Kgarevion: An ai agent for knowledge-intensive biomedical qa, in: *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2024. URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:273186463>.
- [3] R. Islamaj, J. Chan, R. Leaman, Z. Lu, Overview of overview of the medhopqa track at biocreative ix: track description, participation and evaluation of systems for multi-hop medical question answering, in: *BioCreative IX Challenge and Workshop (BC9): Large Language Models for Clinical and Biomedical NLP at the International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI)*, 2025.
- [4] W. Zhu, J. Thomason, R. Jia, Chain-of-questions training with latent answers for robust multistep question answering, in: *Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, 2023. URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:258866054>.
- [5] J. Zhang, H. Zhang, D. Zhang, L. Yong, S. Huang, End-to-end beam retrieval for multi-hop question answering, in: K. Duh, H. Gomez, S. Bethard (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies (Volume 1: Long Papers)*, Association for Computational Linguistics, Mexico City, Mexico, 2024, pp. 1718–1731. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2024.naacl-long.96/>. doi:10.18653/v1/2024.naacl-long.96.
- [6] R. Chen, W. Jiang, C. Qin, I. S. Rawal, C. Tan, D. Choi, B. Xiong, B. Ai, LLM-based multi-hop question answering with knowledge graph integration in evolving environments, in: Y. Al-Onaizan, M. Bansal, Y.-N. Chen (Eds.), *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2024*, Association for Computational Linguistics, Miami, Florida, USA, 2024, pp. 14438–14451. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2024.findings-emnlp.844/>. doi:10.18653/v1/2024.findings-emnlp.844.
- [7] Google, MedGemma Hugging Face, <https://huggingface.co/collections/google/medgemma-release-680aade845f90bec6a3f60c4>, 2025. Accessed: [2025-05-29].
- [8] M. H. Daniel Han, U. team, Unslot, 2023. URL: <http://github.com/unslotai/unslot>.
- [9] G. Team, Gemma 3 (2025). URL: <https://goo.gle/Gemma3Report>.
- [10] A. Q. Jiang, A. Sablayrolles, A. Mensch, C. Bamford, D. S. Chaplot, D. de las Casas, F. Bressand, G. Lengyel, G. Lample, L. Saulnier, L. R. Lavaud, M.-A. Lachaux, P. Stock, T. L. Scao, T. Lavril, T. Wang, T. Lacroix, W. E. Sayed, Mistral 7B, 2023. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.06825>. arXiv:2310.06825.
- [11] Wikipedia contributors, Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/>, 2025.
- [12] N. A. Vasilevsky, N. A. Matentzoglou, S. Toro, J. E. Flack, H. Hegde, D. R. Unni, G. F. Alyea, J. S. Amberger, L. Babb, J. P. Balhoff, T. I. Bingaman, G. A. Burns, O. J. Buske, T. J. Callahan, L. C. Carmody, P. C. Cordo, L. E. Chan, G. S. Chang, S. L. Christiaens, L. C. Daugherty, M. Dumontier, L. E. Failla, M. J. Flowers, H. A. Garrett, J. L. Goldstein, D. Gration, T. Groza, M. Hanauer, N. L. Harris, J. A. Hilton, D. S. Himmelstein, C. T. Hoyt, M. S. Kane, S. Köhler, D. Lagorce, A. Lai, M. Larralde, A. Lock, I. L. Santiago, D. R. Maglott, A. J. Malheiro, B. H. M. Meldal, M. C. Munoz-Torres, T. H. Nelson, F. W. Nicholas, D. Ochoa, D. P. Olson, T. I. Oprea, D. Osumi-Sutherland, H. Parkinson, Z. M. Pendlington, A. Rath, H. L. Rehm, L. Remennik, E. R. Riggs, P. Roncaglia, J. E. Ross, M. F. Shadbolt, K. A. Shefchek, M. N. Similuk, N. Sioutos, D. Smedley, R. Sparks, R. Stefancsik, R. Stephan, A. L. Storm, D. Stupp, G. S. Stupp, J. C. Sundaramurthi, I. Tammen, D. Tay, C. L. Thaxton, E. Valasek, J. Valls-Margarit, A. H. Wagner, D. Welter, P. L. Whetzel, L. L. Whiteman, V. Wood, C. H. Xu, A. Zankl, X. A. Zhang, C. G. Chute, P. N. Robinson, C. J. Mungall, A. Hamosh, M. A. Haendel, Mondo: Unifying diseases for the world, by the world, *medRxiv* (2022). URL: <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/early/2022/05/03/2022.04.13.22273750>. doi:10.1101/2022.04.13.22273750.
- [13] P. Talapova, M. Gargano, N. Matentzoglou, B. Coleman, E. Addo-Lartey, A. Anagnostopoulos,

- J. Anderton, P. Avillach, The human phenotype ontology in 2024: phenotypes around the world. (2024).
- [14] McKusick-Nathans Institute of Genetic Medicine, Johns Hopkins University (Baltimore, MD), Online mendelian inheritance in man, OMIM, 2025. URL: <https://omim.org/>.
- [15] M. Q. Stearns, C. Price, K. A. Spackman, A. Y. Wang, SNOMED clinical terms: overview of the development process and project status, Proc. AMIA Symp. (2001) 662–666.
- [16] L. M. Schriml, E. Mitraha, J. Munro, B. Tauber, M. Schor, L. Nickle, V. Felix, L. Jeng, C. Bearer, R. Lichenstein, K. Bisordi, N. Champion, B. Hyman, D. Kurland, C. P. Oates, S. Kibbey, P. Sreekumar, C. Le, M. Giglio, C. Greene, Human disease ontology 2018 update: classification, content and workflow expansion, Nucleic Acids Research 47 (2018) D955–D962. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky1032>. doi:10.1093/nar/gky1032. arXiv:<https://academic.oup.com/nar/article-pdf/47/D1/D955/27437186/gky1032.pdf>.

Appendix

A. Prompts

In this section, we present the prompts used for our systems.

NER Prompt

You are an information extraction assistant working on biomedical question and answering. Your goal is to extract all biomedical entities from the given text. Your output format MUST always be comma separated entities 'Entities: <ent1>, <ent2>, <ent3>, ...' like in the following example.

Example:

Question: Which virus is associated with causing lymphocytopenia and can lead to AIDS?
Entities: virus, lymphocytopenia, AIDS

Question: What is a common symptom shared by thyroid hormone resistance and goitre?
Entities: symptom, thyroid hormone resistance, goitre

Question: Which protein involved in tight junctions is associated with the skin barrier dysfunction in atopic dermatitis?
Entities: protein, tight junctions, skin barrier dysfunction, atopic dermatitis

Using the same format and logic, extract the entities from the following question:

Question: question

Chain of Thought- Ontology Definitions Prompt

You are an information extraction assistant working on biomedical question answering. Your task is to answer complex biomedical questions that require multi-step reasoning across interconnected entities.

You will receive entities definitions to help answer the question.

Your reasoning process should follow these explicit steps before producing the answer:

1. Identify and list all distinct components or entities in the question.
2. Convert each component into a clear, logically structured subquestion.
3. Independently answer each subquestion using biomedical knowledge.
4. Synthesize the subanswers to derive the final answer using logical reasoning.
5. Return only the final output in strict JSON format.

Output Format Rules:

- Output MUST be a valid JSON object ONLY.
- Do NOT include thoughts, explanations, or markdown.
- JSON must include:

```
{  
  "short_answer": ...,  
  "long_answer": ...  
}
```

Examples:

Example 1:

Question: "Which human chromosome contains the gene that encodes the enzyme that can inactivate antithrombin?"

Short Answer: "Chromosome 11"

Long Answer: "Neutrophil elastase is the enzyme that inactivates antithrombin. In humans, neutrophil elastase is encoded by the ELANE gene, which is found on chromosome 11."

Example 2:

Question: "Which gene mutation is responsible for the syndrome characterized by flattened and deformed vertebrae, developmental delay, and lens coloboma?"

Short Answer: "IRF6"

Long Answer: "The syndrome characterized by flattened and deformed vertebrae, developmental delay, and lens coloboma and dislocation, among others, is called Verloes Van Maldergem Marneffe syndrome, and is also known as microspherophakia-metaphyseal dysplasia. This autosomal dominant inherited syndrome is caused by mutations in the IRF6 gene."

Rules:

1. NO explanations/thoughts/caveats in the final output.
2. ONLY output the JSON answer block.
3. Output MUST begin with {
4. Do NOT include markdown code blocks or any surrounding text.

Final task:

Use the reasoning steps above to answer the following biomedical question.

Definitions:

```
{definitions}
```

Question to answer:

```
{question}
```

Wikipedia prompt

You are an expert biomedical question answering helper. Given a question you answer the question in two ways.

Given a Question, a set of Entities relevant to the question and a portion of each respective Wikipedia page, you will answer the question in two ways. The output format MUST ALWAYS be a Long Answer and a Short Answer. The Short Answer MUST BE JUST the NAME of the entity that answers the question with nothing else, while the long answer is a more detailed explanation of the answer. All your Answers MUST NOT contain any explanations, thoughts, or caveats. If the provided information is not enough, you MUST answer the question with what you know. NEVER mention that the information provided is not enough and do not include any disclaimers. Stick to answering. The following is an example:

—

Question: Which physician, along with Edvard Ehlers, is the Ehlers Danlos syndromes named after?

(...) Entity: Ehlers-Danlos syndromes

Info: Ehlers–Danlos syndromes (EDS) is a group of 14 genetic connective-tissue disorders. Symptoms often include loose joints, joint pain, stretchy velvety skin, and abnormal scar formation. These may be noticed at birth or in early childhood. Complications may include aortic dissection, joint dislocations, scoliosis, chronic pain, or early osteoarthritis. The existing classification was last updated in 2017, when a number of rarer forms of EDS were added. EDS occurs due to mutations in one or more particular genes—there are 19 genes that can contribute to the condition. The specific gene affected determines the type of EDS, though the genetic causes of hypermobile Ehlers–Danlos syndrome are still unknown. Some cases result from a new variation occurring during early development, while others are inherited in an autosomal dominant or recessive manner. Typically, these variations result in defects in the structure or processing of the protein collagen or tenascin. Diagnosis is often based on symptoms, particularly with hypermobile EDS (hEDS), but people may initially be misdiagnosed with hypochondriasis, depression, or myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome. Genetic testing can be used to confirm all types of EDS except hEDS, for which a genetic marker has yet to be discovered. A cure is not yet known, and treatment is supportive in nature. Physical therapy and bracing may help strengthen muscles and support joints. Several medications can help alleviate symptoms of EDS such as pain and blood pressure drugs, which reduce joint pain and complications caused by blood vessel weakness. Some forms of EDS result in a normal life expectancy, but those that affect blood vessels generally decrease it. All forms of EDS can result in fatal outcomes for some patients. While hEDS affects at least one in 5,000 people globally, other types occur at lower frequencies. The prognosis depends on the specific disorder. Excess mobility was first described by Hippocrates in 400 BC. The syndromes are named after two physicians, Edvard Ehlers and Henri-Alexandre Danlos, who described them at the turn of the 20th century.

Short Answer: Henri-Alexandre Danlos. Long Answer: The Ehlers-Danlos syndromes (EDS) are named after two physicians, Edvard Ehlers and Henri-Alexandre Danlos. Edvard Ehlers was a Danish dermatologist who first described the syndrome in 1901. Henri-Alexandre Danlos, a French dermatologist, independently described similar symptoms in 1908. The naming of the condition honors their contributions to the understanding and identification of this group of connective tissue disorders. EDS encompasses a range of inherited conditions characterized by defects in the synthesis of collagen, leading to symptoms such as hypermobile joints, stretchy skin, and abnormal scar formation.

—

Question: {question}